

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Toxin-like peptides in plasma, urine and faecal samples from COVID-19 patients [version 1; peer review: awaiting peer review]

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Abstract

Background: SARS-CoV-2 that causes COVID-19 disease and led to the pandemic currently affecting the world has been broadly investigated. Different studies have been performed to understand the infection mechanism, and the involved human genes, transcripts and proteins. In parallel, numerous clinical extra-pulmonary manifestations co-occurring with COVID-19 disease have been reported and evidence of their severity and persistence is increasing. Whether these manifestations are linked to other disorders co-occurring with SARS-CoV-2 infection, is under discussion. In this work, we report the identification of toxin-like peptides in COVID-19 patients by application of the Liquid Chromatography Surface-Activated Chemical Ionization – Cloud Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry.

Methods: Plasma, urine and faecal samples from COVID-19 patients and

control individuals were analysed to study peptidomic toxins' profiles. Protein precipitation preparation procedure was used for plasma, to remove high molecular weight proteins and efficiently solubilize the peptide fraction; in the case of faeces and urine, direct peptide solubilization was employed.

Results: Toxin-like peptides, almost identical to toxic components of venoms from animals, like conotoxins, phospholipases, phosphodiesterases, zinc metal proteinases, and bradykinins, were identified in samples from COVID-19 patients, but not in control samples.

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Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Conclusions: The presence of toxin-like peptides could potentially be connected to SARS-CoV-2 infection. Their presence suggests a possible association between COVID-19 disease and the release in the body of (oligo-)peptides almost identical to toxic components of venoms from animals. Their involvement in a large set of heterogeneous extra-pulmonary COVID-19 clinical manifestations, like neurological ones, cannot be excluded. Although the presence of each individual symptom is not selective of the disease, their combination might be related to COVID-19 by the coexistence of the panel of the here detected toxin-like peptides. The presence of these peptides opens new scenarios on the aetiology of the COVID-19 clinical symptoms observed up to now, including neurological manifestations.

Keywords

SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, toxin-like peptides

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Introduction

Numerous clinical extra-pulmonary manifestations co-occurring with COVID-19 disease have been reported (e.g. neurological, haemorrhagic, and thrombotic) and evidence of their severity and persistence is increasing. Gupta *et al.* reviewed the extrapulmonary organ-specific pathophysiology of patients with COVID-19, 'to aid clinicians and scientists in recognizing and monitoring the spectrum of manifestations, and in developing research priorities and therapeutic strategies for all organ systems involved'¹. Liotta *et al.* characterized the incidence of neurological manifestations in a cohort of hospitalised patients with confirmed COVID-19: the most frequent were myalgia, headache, encephalopathy, dizziness, dysgeusia, and anosmia; encephalopathy was found to be 'associated with increased morbidity and mortality, independent of respiratory disease severity'². Whether these manifestations are linked to disorders co-occurring with SARS-CoV-2 infection is under discussion, including their concomitant occurrence, which could be strongly related COVID-19 disease. Frontera *et al.*, by conducting a prospective, multi-centre, observational study of hospitalised adults with laboratory-confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection, concluded that 'neurologic disorders were detected in 13.5% of COVID-19 patients during the study timeframe. Many of these neurologic disorders occur commonly among patients with critical illness. Encephalitis, meningitis or myelitis referable to SARS-CoV-2 infection did not occur, though post-infectious Guillain-Barre syndrome was identified. Overall, neurologic disorders in the context of SARS-CoV-2 infection confer a higher risk of in-hospital mortality and reduced likelihood of discharge home'³.

Studies on the use of mass spectrometry in COVID-19 context focus on the search for augmented human inflammatory molecules to be used as biomarkers to assess the severity status of COVID-19 (see for example the work⁴ of Messner and colleagues). Different studies report the use of proteomic approaches to characterise SARS-CoV-2 proteins⁵⁻⁷. Other studies highlight challenges in their use due to the need of enriching the protein fraction to be analysed for maximizing the technology sensitivity.⁸

Liquid Chromatography Surface-Activated Chemical Ionization – Cloud Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry (LC-SACI-CIMS) is reported as a high sensitivity mass spectrometry technique able to maximize the peptide signal intensity⁹⁻¹². We used LC-SACI-CIMS to reveal the presence of metabolites that could explain the clinical descriptions of neurological, coagulation and inflammatory symptoms, and here we present the results of our analyses. We found toxin-like peptides in plasma, urine, and faecal samples from COVID-19 patients, but not in control samples. As our findings do not correspond with current thinking of the aetiology related to the observed clinical manifestations in COVID-19 patients, we feel their immediate sharing with the scientific community is critical.

Methods

Rationale

Liquid Chromatography-Surface Activated Chemical Ionization – Cloud Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry (LC-SACI-CIMS) exhibits a high selectivity in peptide detection thanks to

its ability to selectively isolate peptide ions through an in-source ion mobility (IM) effect. In fact, it allows a selective regulation of the potential difference between the low voltage of the SACI surface (47 V) and the entrance lens (-50 / -600 V), and a selective focalization on solvent ion cloud containing species at low or high m/z ratio. By switching the entrance voltage lens between -50 and -600 V during the analysis, it is possible to separate the low m/z from the high m/z potential signal, to avoid ion trap saturation, and to maximize the number of detected compounds. The mass spectra chemical noise is also strongly reduced due to the lower amounts of solvent cluster ions that are produced in low voltage ionization conditions. Thus, the peptide detection efficiency is strongly increased by the IM selectivity and lower chemical noise with respect to the classical high voltage ionization approaches. Thanks to the specificity of the SACI-CIMS technology in focalizing the solvent ion clouds containing the high m/z (oligo-)peptide species, it was possible to increase the detection efficiency.

In the use of LC-SACI-CIMS, the following strategies have been adopted:

- To reduce the presence of contamination as much as possible and to avoid the formation of acetonitrile polymers occurring in acid conditions (as reported by Eizo *et al.*¹³), formic acid was not added to the CH₃CN chromatographic phase.
- To separate low from high m/z solvent ion clusters by reducing the ion trap saturation, the space/charge effect, and by increasing the detected compounds recovery, LC-SACI-CIMS entrance lens voltage was switched between -50 and -600 V every 10 ms during the analysis.
- To enhance the SACI ionization efficiency, NH₄HCO₃ was added to the samples. As reported in the literature^{14,15}, the peptide ionization efficiency (and consequently the sensitivity) is enhanced in SACI conditions when ionic salts are present in the sample, due to peptide ion specific coordination.
- To decrease the total run time, a shot gun chromatographic gradient was used to desalt the sample.
- To avoid sample molecular profile alteration, and to evaluate the potential biological activities of the circulating species, no enzymatic digestion was applied to samples.
- To normalize the m/z signal intensity, 5 μ L of standard ESI tune mix (Agilent, USA) were added to each sample extract.

Chemicals

NH₄HCO₃, methanol, acetonitrile and formic acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy). Bi-distilled water was purchased from VWR (Milan, Italy).

Cohort

Samples used in the present study: plasma samples collected from 15 COVID-19 patients from different cities of Italy and from five control individuals (i.e. negative to SARS-CoV-2

tests and not affected by cancer or autoimmune diseases); urine samples collected from two additional COVID-19 patients and from two control individuals; stool samples from three COVID-19 patients and from three control individuals. The human biological samples used in the experimentation were collected and used with the expressed free and informed written consent, of the person from whom the material was taken, according to current legislation. The study received approval from “Comitato Etico Campania Sud” (n.36/2021, request submitted on 06-05-2020).

Sample preparation

Plasma. Each plasma sample was treated as follows: 5 μL of CH_3CN were added to 50 μL of plasma and vortexed for one minute. The procedure was repeated 10 times. Then the sample was centrifuged at 1,500 g for 10 minutes and two 100 μL aliquots of supernatant were dried and resuspended in 70 μL of NH_4HCO_3 50 mmol. The solution was analysed by LC-SACI-CIMS (see *Rationale*).

Urine. Each urine sample was treated as follows: an equivalent volume of bi-distilled water was added, followed by centrifugation at 1,500 g for 10 minutes. 100 μL were dried and resuspended in 70 μL of NH_4HCO_3 50 mmol. The sample was analysed by LC-SACI-CIMS (see *Rationale*).

Stool. Each stool sample was treated as described by Cristoni *et al.*¹¹ and analysed by LC-SACI-CIMS (see *Rationale*).

Liquid chromatography

The Ultimate 3000 LC (by ThermoFisher) was used to achieve separation of analytes for each sample prior to mass spectrometry (MS) analysis. A reversed phase Kinetex C-18 LC column (50 \times 2.1 mm; particle size, 5 μm ; pore size, 100 \AA , by Phenomenex, USA) was used. The eluent flow was 0.25 mL/min and the injection volume was 15 μL . The mobile phases were:

- A. 0.2% (v/v) formic acid (HCOOH)
- B. acetonitrile (CH_3CN)

The elution gradient was: 2% (v/v) of B between 0 and 2 min; 2 to 30% between 2 and 7 min; 30 to 80% between 7 and 9 min; 80% between 9 and 12 min; 80-2% between 12 and 12.1 min. The column was rebalanced with 2% of B between 12.1 and 17 min.

Mass spectrometry

All samples were analysed for the presence of proteins with potential toxic effect by using the LC-SACI-CIMS as already described in the literature⁹⁻¹². Samples were analysed with an ORBITRAP mass spectrometer (Breme, Germany) coupled to a surface-activated chemical ionization (SACI) source and operated in positive ion mode.

The surface voltage was 47 V and the entrance lens was switched between -50 and -600 V each 10 ms. Auxiliary gas: 2 L / min; Nebulizer gas: 80 psi; Temperature: 40 $^\circ\text{C}$. Full

scan spectra were acquired in the 40–3,500 m/z range for non-targeted metabolomics/proteomics analyses to detect analytes. The same m/z range was used for both discovery and selective biomarker identification, and to standardize (primarily in terms of scan rate) the instrument. The software used for data elaboration is SANIST, a modified version of the Global Proteome Machine (GPM, <https://www.thegpm.org/GPM/>), implanted as described in 9–12. SANIST output files are available as supplementary material¹⁶ (see section *Data availability*).

SANIST software here used is freely available, upon email request to CranioMed group (dir.brogna@craniomed.it).

Mass spectrometry on samples was performed with collision-induced dissociation using data dependent scan and helium as the collision gas. The ion trap was applied to isolate and fragment the precursor ions (windows of isolation, \pm 0.3 m/z ; collision energy, 30% of its maximum value, which was 5V peak to peak), and the ORBITRAP mass analyser was used to obtain fragments with an extremely accurate m/z ratio (resolution 15,000; m/z error <10 ppm).

Data elaboration

Detected high m/z peptides were used to identify toxins thanks due to the selectivity given by their long chain.

The complete UniprotKB set of manually reviewed venom proteins and toxins (UniprotKB, Animal toxin annotation project. <https://www.uniprot.org/program/Toxins>, Accessed October 4, 2020), mixed with a subset of non-venom proteins and toxins from UniprotKB database¹⁷ was used as reference protein dataset in order to give statistical significance to the results.

TBLASTN¹⁸ was run at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) website¹⁹ with default options and parameters, with the exception of the following ones: max target sequences = 1,000; expect threshold = 100; word size = 3; gap cost existence = 9; gap cost extension = 1; filter of low complexity regions = No. Searches have been performed versus: Nucleotide collection (nr/nt); Reference RNA sequences (refseq_rna); RefSeq Genome Database (refseq_genomes); Whole-genome shotgun contigs (wgs) from metagenomic experiments; Sequence Read Archive (SRA) sequences from metagenomic experiments; Transcriptome Shotgun Assembly (TSA); Patent sequences (pat); Human RefSeqGene sequences (RefSeq_Gene); Betacoronavirus Genbank sequence dataset.

The information reported in **Table 1** has been retrieved from the UniprotKB database and from the NCBI Taxonomy database²⁰, after confirmation by BLAST sequence comparison analysis¹⁸.

SANIST was set to perform the database search considering all potential protein points and post-translational modifications, and to consider proton rearrangements. No enzyme cutting rules were specified, but all the protein subsequence combinations were considered. Database search calculation

Table 1. Overview of candidate proteins on which toxin-like peptides have been mapped. Thirty-six candidate protein sequences on which the identified toxin-like peptides have been mapped are here reported, together with information retrieved from UniProtKB and NCBI Taxonomy databases. The table is split in three sections according to the phylum of the reported species: *Chordata* (green), *Echinodermata* (pink), *Mollusca* (azure).

UNIPROTKB CANDIDATE'S INFORMATION						TAXONOMY CANDIDATE'S INFORMATION					
AC	ID	Status	Protein name	ENZYME EC	Other name(s)	Length (aa)	ID	Species	Phylum - Family	Organism's common name(s)	
Q8AY46	VKTHB_BUNCA	reviewed	Kunitz-type serine protease inhibitor homolog beta-bungarotoxin B1 chain	NA	-	85	92438	<i>Bungarus Canadus</i>	Chordata - <i>Elapidae</i>	. Malayan krait	
A6MEY4	PA2B_BUNFA	reviewed	Basic phospholipase A2 BFPA	EC 3.1.1.4	. Antimicrobial phospholipase A2 . Phosphatidylcholine 2-acylhydrolase (svPLA2)	145	8613	<i>Bungarus fasciatus</i>	Chordata - <i>Elapidae</i>	. Banded krait . Pseudoboa fasciata	
F5CPF1	PA235_MICAT	reviewed	Phospholipase A2 MALT0035C	EC 3.1.1.4	. Phospholipase A2 MALT0035C (svPLA2)	142	129457	<i>Micrurus altirostris</i>	Chordata - <i>Elapidae</i>	. Uruguayan coral snake . Elaps altirostris	
A8QL59	VM3_NAJAT	reviewed	Zinc metalloproteinase-disintegrin-like NaMP	EC 3.4.24.-	. Snake venom metalloproteinase (SVMP)	621	8656	<i>Naja atra</i>	Chordata - <i>Elapidae</i>	. Chinese cobra	
Q9I900	PA2AD_NAJSP	reviewed	Acidic phospholipase A2 D	EC 3.1.1.4	. svPLA2 . APLA . Phosphatidylcholine 2-acylhydrolase	146	33626	<i>Naja sputatrix</i>	Chordata - <i>Elapidae</i>	. Malayan spitting cobra . Naja najasputatrix	
Q58L90	FA5V_OXYMI	reviewed	Venom prothrombin activator: omicarin-C non-catalytic subunit	NA	. vPA . Venom coagulation factor Va-like protein <i>Cleaved into 2 chains</i>	1460	111177	<i>Oxyuranus microlepidotus</i>	Chordata - <i>Elapidae</i>	. Inland taipan . Diemenia microlepidota	
Q58L91	FA5V_OXYSU	reviewed	Venom prothrombin activator: oscutarin-C non-catalytic subunit	NA	. vPA . Venom coagulation factor Va-like protein <i>Cleaved into 2 chains</i>	1459	8668	<i>Oxyuranus scutellatus</i>	Chordata - <i>Elapidae</i>	. Coastal taipan	
Q9W7J9	3S34_PSETE	reviewed	Short neurotoxin 4	NA	. SNTX4 . Alpha-neurotoxin 4	79	8673	<i>Pseudonaja textilis</i>	Chordata - <i>Elapidae</i>	. Eastern brown snake	
P23028	PA2AD_PSETE	reviewed	Acidic phospholipase A2 homolog textilotoxin D chain	NA	. svPLA2 homolog	152	8673	<i>Pseudonaja textilis</i>	Chordata - <i>Elapidae</i>	. Eastern brown snake	
Q593B6	FA5_PSETE	reviewed	Coagulation factor V	NA	<i>Cleaved into 2 chains</i>	1459	8673	<i>Pseudonaja textilis</i>	Chordata - <i>Elapidae</i>	. Eastern brown snake	

UNIPROTKB CANDIDATE'S INFORMATION						TAXONOMY CANDIDATE'S INFORMATION				
AC	ID	Status	Protein name	ENZYME EC	Length (aa)	ID	Species	Phylum - Family	Organism's common name(s)	
Q75ZN0	FA5V_PSETE	reviewed	Venom prothrombin activator pserutarin-C non-catalytic subunit	NA	1460	8673	<i>Pseudonaja textilis</i>	Chordata - <i>Elapidae</i>	. Eastern brown snake	
Q2XXQ3	CRVP1_PSEPL	reviewed	Cysteine-rich venom protein ENH1	NA	239	338839	<i>Pseudoferania polylepsis</i>	Chordata - <i>Homalopsidae</i>	. Macleay's water snake . Enhydriis polylepsis	
Q9PW56	BNP2_BOTJA	reviewed	Bradykinin -potentiating and C-type natriuretic peptides	NA	265	8724	<i>Bothrops jararaca</i>	Chordata - <i>Viperidae</i>	. Jararaca	
A8YPR6	SVML_ECHOC	reviewed	Snake venom metalloprotease inhibitor	NA	308	99586	<i>Echis ocellatus</i>	Chordata - <i>Viperidae</i>	. Ocellated saw-scaled viper	
Q698K8	VM2L4_GLOBR	reviewed	Zinc metalloprotease /disintegrin [Fragment]	EC 3.4.24-	319	259325	<i>Gloydius brevicaudus</i>	Chordata - <i>Viperidae</i>	. Korean slamosa snake . Agkistrodon halys brevicaudus	
Q8AWI5	VM3HA_GLOHA	reviewed	Zinc metalloprotease-disintegrin -like halysase	EC 3.4.24-	610	8714	<i>Gloydius halys</i>	Chordata - <i>Viperidae</i>	. Chinese water moccasin . Agkistrodon halys	
P82662	3L26_OPHHA	reviewed	Alpha- neurotoxin	NA	91	8665	<i>Ophiophagus hannah</i>	Chordata - <i>Viperidae</i>	. King cobra . Naja hannah	

UNIPROTKB CANDIDATES INFORMATION							TAXONOMY CANDIDATES INFORMATION				
AC	ID	Status	Protein name	ENZYME EC	Other name(s)	Length (aa)	ID	Species	Phylum - Family	Organism's common name(s)	
Q2PG83	PAZA_PROEL	reviewed	Acidic phospholipase A2 PePLA2	EC 3.1.1.4	. Phosphatidylcholine 2-acylhydrolase (svPLA2)	138	88086	<i>Protobothrops elegans</i>	Chordata - <i>Viperidae</i>	. Elegant pitviper . Trimeresurus elegans	
P06860	PA2BX_PROFL	reviewed	Basic phospholipase A2 PL-X	EC 3.1.1.4	. Phosphatidylcholine 2-acylhydrolase (svPLA2)	122	88087	<i>Protobothrops flavoviridis</i>	Chordata - <i>Viperidae</i>	. Habu . Trimeresurus flavoviridis	
P0C7P5	BNP_PROFL	reviewed	Bradykinin-potentiating and C-type natriuretic peptides	NA	. BPP-CNP Cleaved into 6 chains	193	88087	<i>Protobothrops flavoviridis</i>	Chordata - <i>Viperidae</i>	. Habu . Trimeresurus flavoviridis	
Q3C2C2	PA21_ACAPL	reviewed	Phospholipase A2 AP-PLA2-I	EC 3.1.1.4	. Phosphatidylcholine 2-acylhydrolase (svPLA2)	159	133434	<i>Acanthaster planci</i>	Echinodermata - <i>Acanthasteridae</i>	. Crown-of-thorns starfish	
D6C4M3	CU96_CONCL	reviewed	Conotoxin C19.6	NA	. Conotoxin C19.6	81	1736779	<i>Californiconus californicus</i>	Mollusca - <i>Conidae</i>	. California cone - . Conus californicus	
D2Y488	VKT1A_CONCL	reviewed	Kunitz-type serine protease inhibitor conotoxin Ca19.1a	NA	-	78	1736779	<i>Californiconus californicus</i>	Mollusca - <i>Conidae</i>	. California cone . Conus californicus	
D6C4J8	CUE9_CONCL	reviewed	Conotoxin C14.9	NA	-	78	1736779	<i>Californiconus californicus</i>	Mollusca - <i>Conidae</i>	. California cone . Conus californicus	
P0DPT2	CA1B_CONCT	reviewed	Alpha-conotoxin C1B [Fragment]	NA	. C1.2	41	101291	<i>Conus catus</i>	Mollusca - <i>Conidae</i>	. Cat cone	
V5V893	CQG3_CONFL	reviewed	Conotoxin Fla16d	NA	. Conotoxin Fla16d Cleaved into 2 chains	76	101302	<i>Conus flavidus</i>	Mollusca - <i>Conidae</i>	. Yellow Pacific cone	
P58924	CS8A_CONGE	reviewed	Sigma-conotoxin GVIIIA	NA	. Sigma-conotoxin GVIIIA	88	6491	<i>Conus geographus</i>	Mollusca - <i>Conidae</i>	. Geography cone . Nubecula geographus	
P0DM19	NF2_CONMR	reviewed	Conotoxin Mr15.2	NA	. Conotoxin Mr15.2 (Mr094)	92	42752	<i>Conus marmoreus</i>	Mollusca - <i>Conidae</i>	. Marble cone	
P0C1N5	M3G_CONMR	reviewed	Conotoxin mr3g	NA	. Conotoxin mr3g (Mr3.6)	68	42752	<i>Conus marmoreus</i>	Mollusca - <i>Conidae</i>	. Marble cone	

UNIPROT KB CANDIDATE'S INFORMATION							TAXONOMY CANDIDATE'S INFORMATION			
AC	ID	Status	Protein name	ENZYME EC	Other name(s)	Length (aa)	ID	Species	Phylum - Family	Organism's common name(s)
D2DGD8	I361_CONPL	reviewed	Conotoxin Pu6.1	NA	-	83	93154	<i>Conus pulicarius</i>	Mollusca - Conidae	. Flea-bite cone
P0C8U9	CA15_CONPL	reviewed	Alpha-conotoxin-like Pu1.5	NA	-	81	93154	<i>Conus pulicarius</i>	Mollusca - Conidae	. Flea-bite cone
A1X8B8	CAL_CONQU	reviewed	Putative alpha-conotoxin Qc alphaL-1	NA	. QcaL-1	68	101313	<i>Conus quercinus</i>	Mollusca - Conidae	. Oak cone
P58786	COW_CONRA	reviewed	Contryphan-R	NA	. Bromocontryphan Cleaved into 2 chains	63	61198	<i>Conus radiatus</i>	Mollusca - Conidae	. Rayed cone
P58811	CA1A_CONTU	reviewed	Rho-conotoxin TIA	NA	. Rho-TIA	58	6495	<i>Conus tulipa</i>	Mollusca - Conidae	. Fish-hunting cone snail . Tulip cone
Q5K0C5	016A_CONVR	reviewed	Conotoxin 10	NA	-	79	89427	<i>Conus virgo</i>	Mollusca - Conidae	. Virgin cone
B3FIA5	CVFA_CONVR	reviewed	Conotoxin V115a	NA	. Conotoxin V115.I	74	8765	<i>Conus virgo</i>	Mollusca - Conidae	. Virgin cone

was performed by means of General Processing Graphic Processing Units (GPGPU).

The MS data are available on the ZENODO platform¹⁶ (see section *Data availability*).

Results and discussion

The presence of (oligo-)peptides characterised as toxic components of animal venoms was observed in plasma and urine samples from SARS-CoV-2 infected patients and never in plasma, urine and faecal samples from control individuals. Examples of SACI-CIMS chromatograms are reported in **Figure 1** and **Figure 2** (panels a and b), showing the spectra acquired by means of the LC-SACI-CIMS technology. **Figure 2c and d** show the spectra obtained using ESI extracted at the same retention time. SACI-CIMS give rise to higher signal intensities probably due to the low ion trap saturation.

Several (oligo-)peptides (between 70 and 115, depending on the analysed sample) matched to different animal venom proteins and toxins like conotoxins, phospholipases A2, metalloproteinases (86% of assignments have a $-\log(e)$ higher than 25). An overview of 36 proteins covered by the toxin-like peptides found is reported in **Table 1**; details of $-\log(e)$ and false discovery rates are reported in **Table 2**. Examples of mass spectra peptide characterization together with the peptide ion fragmentation pathways are shown in **Figure 3a**. All the MS/MS signal were assigned to the different N-terminal y,z (blue and purple colour) and c-terminal b,c (red and yellow colour) fragmentation series (see **Figure 3b** for fragmentation series details). In the defined SACI-CIMS conditions, doubly charged m/z ion of medium-high molecular weight peptide species are produced, allowing high identification accuracy, in line with what is already described in the literature that high identification statistical rates are achieved

Figure 1. (a) Base peak LC Full Scan (MS), tandem mass (MS/MS) chromatogram of an extracted plasma sample of a patient and a control subject and (b) a blow-up of a specific chromatogram region (5.713–5.719 min). The blow-up shows the four regions of data acquisition: 1) Full scan mass spectrum originated by the cloud containing low m/z ratio molecular species; 2) Tandem mass spectra (MS/MS) mass spectrum originated by the cloud containing low m/z ratio molecular species; 3) Full scan mass spectrum originated by the cloud containing medium-high (MedHigh) m/z ratio molecular species; 4) Tandem mass spectra (MS/MS) mass spectrum originated by the cloud containing medium-high (MedHigh) m/z ratio molecular species.

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 2. Examples of full scan mass spectra, obtained by analysing a COVID-19 positive urine sample and acquired focusing solvent ion cloud species containing **a)** low, **b)** high m/z species extracted in the 5.713–5.719 min chromatographic region and ESI full scan mass spectrum obtained analysing the same sample and extracting the signal at the same retention time extracting **c)** low and **d)** high m/z ratio.

Table 2. List of proteins and the related $-\log(e)$ and false discovery ratio (FDR) expressed as p value.

Protein	ID	Database	$-\log(e)$	FDR p value
Conotoxin Pu6.1	D2DGD8	Uniprot	75	0.001
Conotoxin Vi15a	B3FIA5	Uniprot	89	0.005
Putative alpha-conotoxin Qc alphaL-1	A1X8B8	Uniprot	76	0.005
Conotoxin 10	Q5K0C5	Uniprot	76	0.001
Rho-conotoxin TIA	P58811	Uniprot	54	0.001
Kunitz-type serine protease inhibitor conotoxin Cal9.1a	D2Y488	Uniprot	67	0.001
Alpha-conotoxin Pu1.5	P0C8U9	Uniprot	57	0.002
Conotoxin Fla16d	V5V893	Uniprot	67	0.003
Phospholipase A2 MALT0035C	F5CPF1	Uniprot	87	0.003
Phospholipase A2 AP-PLA2-I	Q3C2C2	Uniprot	81	0.004
Acidic phospholipase A2 PePLA2	Q2PG83	Uniprot	66	0.001
Basic phospholipase A2 BFPA	A6MEY4	Uniprot	69	0.001
Basic phospholipase A2 PL-X	P06860	Uniprot	70	0.001
Complement factor B Ba fragment	Q91900	Uniprot	74	0.001
Acidic phospholipase A2 homolog textilotoxin D chain	P23028-1	Uniprot	73	0.002
Acidic phospholipase A2 homolog textilotoxin D chain	P23028-2	Uniprot	65	0.002
Venom prothrombin activator pseutarin-C non-catalytic subunit	Q7SZN0	Uniprot	60	0.002
Coagulation factor V	Q593B6	Uniprot	61	
Venom prothrombin activator oscutarin-C non-catalytic subunit	Q58L91	Uniprot	87	0.001
Short neurotoxin 4	Q9W7J9	Uniprot	69	0.001
Conotoxin Cl9.6	D6C4M3	Uniprot	58	0.002
Zinc metalloproteinase-disintegrin-like halysase	Q8AWI5	Uniprot	57	0.003
Alpha-elapitoxin-Oh2b	P82662	Uniprot	96	0.003
Sigma-conotoxin GVIIIA	P58924	Uniprot	43	0.002
Conotoxin Mr15.2	P0DM19	Uniprot	47	0.001
Conotoxin mr3g	P0C1N5	Uniprot	74	0.001
Contryphan-R	P58786	Uniprot	58	0.002
Snake venom metalloprotease inhibitor 02D01	A8YPR6	Uniprot	43	0.002
Bradykinin-potentiating and C-type natriuretic peptides	P0C7P5	Uniprot	51	0.003
Bradykinin-potentiating and C-type natriuretic peptides	Q9PW56	Uniprot	51	0.003
Zinc metalloproteinase/ disintegrin	Q698K8	Uniprot	49	0.004

analysing peptide doubly charged species with medium high molecular weight. Different fragmentation anomalies with proton rearrangements have also been detected and considered in phase of data elaboration. Only mass spectra exhibiting a

statistical $-\log(e)$ score higher than 10 and a false discovery rate lower than 0.05 were considered for the identification (see [Figure 3c](#)). False discovery rate and statistical score were estimated by means of reverse sequence approach.

Figure 3. Examples of mass spectra peptide characterization together with the peptide ion fragmentation pathways. Example of how MS/MS signal were assigned to the different N-terminal y,z (blue and purple colour in panel **a**) and c-terminal b,c (red and yellow colour) fragmentation series (detailed in panel **b**). Only mass spectra exhibiting a statistical -log(e) score higher that 10 and a false discovery rate lower than 0.05 were considered for the identification (reported in panel **c**). False discovery rate and statistical score were estimated by means of reverse sequence approach.

Some of the toxin-like peptides found mapped on the same reference protein (UniprotKB: D2DGD8), are reported in **Figure 4**: these peptides were found in the five plasma samples and in the three faecal samples.

The types of toxic-like peptides found resemble known conotoxins, phospholipases A2, metalloproteinases, prothrombin

activators, coagulation factors, usually present in animal venoms, which are known to have high specificity and affinity towards human ion channels, receptors, and transporters of the nervous system, like the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor.

The same results have been observed in an additional set of 10 plasma samples from 10 different patients.

D2DGD8 - I361_CONPL Conotoxin Pu6.1 (*Conus pulicarius*)

Figure 4. Alignment of toxin-like peptides to Conotoxin Pu6.1. Conotoxin Pu6.1 from *Conus pulicarius* (UniprotKB:D2DGD8) is aligned with the toxin-like peptides identified in four out of five plasma samples. Being the protein secreted and cleaved, leader-region pro-peptide and mature cysteine rich domains are highlighted in green, yellow and red, respectively. Each identified toxin-like peptide is named according to the sample of origin and its uniqueness. For each of them, the number reported in square brackets indicates the number of identical toxin-like peptides identified in the same sample.

What follows is our attempt to elaborate a potential relation between their presence and extra-pulmonary COVID-19 symptomatology.

Conotoxins

Conotoxins are neurotoxic peptides isolated from the venom of marine (genus *Conus*) cone snails. In their mature form, they consist of 10 to 30 amino acid residues, with often one or more disulphide bonds, which are used to classify them in structural classes (μ -conotoxins, ω -conotoxins, and α -conotoxins are the major classes). The mechanism of action of conotoxins is not yet fully understood²¹. Studies have found that they are able to modulate the activity of several receptors, including ion channels, nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs) and acetylcholine-degrading enzymes (acetylcholinesterases), thus resulting in the alteration of acetylcholine levels and of cholinergic transmission²²⁻²⁴. Regarding cholinesterases, a potential association between cholinesterase levels and severity of pneumonia in COVID-19 patients has been proposed²⁵.

The presence of conotoxin peptides might explain the occurrence of many symptoms (like hyposmia, hypogeusia and the signs typical of Guillain-Barre syndrome) observed in some COVID-19 patients. Their presence can alter normal functioning of ion channels, nicotinic acetylcholine receptors and of acetylcholine levels.

Phospholipases A2

Phospholipases A2 (PLA₂, E.C. 3.1.1.4) hydrolyse phospholipids and lead to release of lysophosphatidic acid and arachidonic acid²⁶. Arachidonic acid is a major precursor of many pro-inflammatory mediators like leukotriene, thromboxane and prostaglandin; as a consequence, abnormal presence of active PLA₂ can induce severe inflammation²⁷. In animal venoms, PLA₂ act as neurotoxic proteins: they hydrolyse membrane phospholipids of the motor nerve terminal, and the

plasma membrane of skeletal muscle, thus triggering a severe inflammatory degenerative response, which in turn leads to degeneration of the nerve terminal and skeletal muscle²⁶. The drug dexamethasone can inhibit prostaglandins synthesis and leukotriene formation²⁸. As dexamethasone is still the only therapeutic shown to be effective against the novel coronavirus in patients²⁹ with severe symptoms, it can be that the positive effect of this drug on COVID-19 patients is also due to the reduction of the here identified PLA₂-like peptides.

Metalloproteinases

The last example of identified toxin-like peptides is those recognised as metalloproteinases present in animal venoms, zinc-dependent enzymes of varying molecular weight having multidomain organization. These toxic enzymes cause haemorrhage, local myonecrosis, skin damage, and inflammatory reaction³⁰. It has been reported that symptomatic COVID-19 patients have significantly lower zinc levels in comparison to controls and that zinc deficient patients develop more complications³¹. The presence of this specific group of toxin-like peptides, which capture zinc, can be one of the reasons for such significantly low zinc levels in symptomatic COVID-19 patients.

Similarity searches by TBLASTN¹⁴ with relaxed parameters at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) website (see Methods) revealed (in addition to mRNA sequences from the animal species reported in Table 1) almost identical short stretches (up to 10 amino acids) of these peptides in potential coding regions of many bacterial and viral sequences, but no long potential coding frame entirely covering any of them was found. Consequently, at the time of writing we have not yet identified the “genetic source” of these peptides, which could be:

- The SARS-CoV-2 RNA genome with its protein reading set, as proposed by Brogna³², who reported the identification in SARS-CoV-2 RNA of many regions

encoding for oligopeptides (four–five amino acids long) identical to neurotoxin peptides typical of animal venoms.

- The SARS-CoV-2 genome directly read by bacteria, assuming that the SARS-CoV-2 genome, or parts thereof, is capable of replicating with a possible ‘bacteriophage-like’ mode of action, as previously described³³.
- Genomes of bacteria, which, as a reaction to the presence of the virus, secrete these peptides. This could happen by using still not well known and debated mechanisms, like alternative reading due to rRNA sequence heterogeneity (as described in 34,35), or the involvement of small bacterial ncRNA (sRNAs), known to be key players of gene regulation under conditions like stress response, quorum sensing, or virulence (in this context, in 1984 Coleman *et al.* reported the *micF* non-coding RNA as a functional bacterial sRNA³⁶).
- A combination of the above e.g. the ‘toxin’ genetic code is present in the bacteria and expression may be triggered by SARS-CoV-2, acting like temperate bacteriophages, which are known to interact with bacteria so that they express (or not) certain genes, as described by Carey *et al.*³⁷.

A detailed 3D structural similarity analysis between the toxin-like peptides found and reference proteins has not yet been conducted. Accordingly, at the time of writing, we can only speculate that these toxin-like peptides are involved in the clinical extra-pulmonary manifestations in symptomatic COVID-19 patients. According to our knowledge, these toxin-like peptides have never been searched in animals considered reservoirs of SARS-CoVs.

Conclusions

The presence of (oligo-)peptides almost identical to toxic components of venoms from animals has been observed. Data and results reported here suggest an association between COVID-19 disease and the release in the body of these, and raise a series of questions:

- Are these findings in line with what was proposed by Tizabi *et al.*³⁸, i.e. a potential therapeutic role for nicotine, nicotinic agonists, or positive allosteric modulators of nicotinic cholinergic receptors in COVID-19?
- If induced by SARS-CoV-2, can the production of toxin-like peptides be involved in the neurological disorders and injuries observed in hospitalized COVID-19 patients?
- If induced by SARS-CoV-2, can the production of toxin-like peptides influence complex diseases apparently triggered or enhanced by COVID-19, like e.g. Guillain-Barré Syndrome³⁹ or Parkinson’s disease⁴⁰?
- Are toxin-like peptides associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection or to other viral infections or, more in general, is their presence related to sickness condition?

- Are our findings supporting the suggestion made by the iVAMP Consortium⁴¹ on the relationships between animal venom glands and microorganisms’ microenvironments?

We consider that the immediate sharing of these results can contribute to the untangling of the multifaceted set of clinical manifestations in symptomatic COVID-19 patients, and to the further understanding of the mechanisms involved.

Data availability

Underlying data

Uniprot: Kunitz-type serine protease inhibitor homolog beta-bungarotoxin B1 chain [*Bungarus candidus* (Malayan krait)]. Accession number Q8AY46, <https://identifiers.org/uniprot:Q8AY46>

Uniprot: Basic phospholipase A2 BFFA, svPLA2, EC 3.1.1.4 (Antimicrobial phospholipase A2) (Phosphatidylcholine 2-acylhydrolase) [*Bungarus fasciatus* (Banded krait) (Pseudoboa fasciata)]. Accession number A6MEY4, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:A6MEY4>

Uniprot: Phospholipase A2 MALT0035C, svPLA2, EC 3.1.1.4 [*Micrurus altirostris* (Uruguayan coral snake) (Elaps altirostris)]. Accession number F5CPF1, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:F5CPF1>

Uniprot: Zinc metalloproteinase-disintegrin-like NaMP, EC 3.4.24.- (Snake venom metalloproteinase, SVMP) [*Naja atra* (Chinese cobra)]. Accession number A8QL59, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:A8QL59>

Uniprot: Acidic phospholipase A2 D, svPLA2, EC 3.1.1.4 (APLA) (Phosphatidylcholine 2-acylhydrolase) [*Naja sputatrix* (Malayan spitting cobra) (*Naja naja sputatrix*)]. Accession number Q9I900, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q9I900>

Uniprot: Venom prothrombin activator omicarin-C non-catalytic subunit, vPA (Venom coagulation factor Va-like protein) [Cleaved into: Omicarin-C non-catalytic subunit heavy chain; Omicarin-C non-catalytic subunit light chain] [*Oxyuranus microlepidotus* (Inland taipan) (*Diemenia microlepidota*)]. Accession number A58L90, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q58L90>

Uniprot: Venom prothrombin activator oscutarin-C non-catalytic subunit, vPA (Venom coagulation factor Va-like protein) [Cleaved into: Oscutarin-C non-catalytic subunit heavy chain; Oscutarin-C non-catalytic subunit light chain] [*Oxyuranus scutellatus* (Coastal taipan)]. Accession number Q58L91, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q58L91>

Uniprot: Short neurotoxin 4, SNTX4 (Alpha-neurotoxin 4) [*Pseudonaja textilis* (Eastern brown snake)]. Accession number Q9W7J9, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q9W7J9>

Uniprot: Acidic phospholipase A2 homolog textilotoxin D chain, svPLA2 homolog [*Pseudonaja textilis* (Eastern brown

snake)]. Accession number P23028, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:P23028>

Uniprot: Coagulation factor V [Cleaved into: Coagulation factor V heavy chain; Coagulation factor V light chain] [*Pseudonaja textilis* (Eastern brown snake)]. Accession number Q593B6, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q593B6>

Uniprot: Venom prothrombin activator psetarin-C non-catalytic subunit, PCNS, vPA (Venom coagulation factor Va-like protein) [Cleaved into: Psetarin-C non-catalytic subunit heavy chain; Psetarin-C non-catalytic subunit light chain] [*Pseudonaja textilis* (Eastern brown snake)]. Accession number Q7SZN0, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q7SZN0>

Uniprot: Cysteine-rich venom protein ENH1, CRVP (Cysteine-rich secretory protein ENH1, CRISP-ENH1) [*Pseudoferania polylepis* (Macleay's water snake) (Enhydriis polylepis)]. Accession number Q2XXQ3, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q2XXQ3>

Uniprot: Bradykinin-potentiating and C-type natriuretic peptides (Brain BPP-CNP, bBPP-CNP) (Evasin-CNP) [Cleaved into 12 chains] [*Bothrops jararaca* (Jararaca)]. Accession number Q9PW56, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q9PW56>

Uniprot: Snake venom metalloprotease inhibitor 02D01 (02E11) (10F07) (Svmpi-Eoc7) [Cleaved into 15 chains] [*Echis ocellatus* (Ocellated saw-scaled viper)]. Accession number A8YPR6, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:A8YPR6>

Uniprot: Zinc metalloproteinase/disintegrin [Cleaved into: Snake venom metalloproteinase brevilysin L4, SVMP (Snake venom metalloproteinase hxl-1, EC 3.4.24.-) ; Disintegrin brevicandin-1a; Disintegrin brevicandin-1b (Disintegrin adinbitor) (Disintegrin halystatin)] [*Gloydius brevicaudus* (Korean slamosa snake) (Agkistrodon halys brevicaudus)]. Accession number Q698K8, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q698K8>

Uniprot: Zinc metalloproteinase-disintegrin-like halysase, EC 3.4.24.- (Snake venom metalloproteinase, SVMP) (Vascular apoptosis-inducing protein, VAP) [*Gloydius halys* (Chinese water mocassin) (Agkistrodon halys)]. Accession number Q8AWI5, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q8AWI5>

Uniprot: Alpha-elapitoxin-Oh2b, Alpha-EPTX-Oh2b (Alpha-neurotoxin) (LNTX3) (Long neurotoxin OH-6A/OH-6B) (OH-3) [*Ophiophagus hannah* (King cobra) (Naja hannah)]. Accession number P82662, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:P82662>

Uniprot: Acidic phospholipase A2 PePLA2, svPLA2, EC 3.1.1.4 (Phosphatidylcholine 2-acylhydrolase) [*Protobothrops elegans* (Elegant pitviper) (Trimeresurus elegans)]. Accession number Q2PG83, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q2PG83>

Uniprot: Basic phospholipase A2 PL-X, svPLA2, EC 3.1.1.4 (Phosphatidylcholine 2-acylhydrolase) [*Protobothrops elegans* (Elegant pitviper) (Trimeresurus elegans)]. Accession number P06860, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:P06860>

Uniprot: Bradykinin-potentiating and C-type natriuretic peptides (BPP-CNP) [Cleaved into six chains] [*Protobothrops flavoviridis* (Habu) (Trimeresurus flavoviridis)]. Accession number P0C7P5, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:P0C7P5>

Uniprot: Phospholipase A2 AP-PLA2-I, PLA2, EC 3.1.1.4 (Phosphatidylcholine 2-acylhydrolase 2) [*Acanthaster planci* (Crown-of-thorns starfish)]. Accession number Q2C2C2, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q2C2C2>

Uniprot: Conotoxin Cl9.6 [*Californiconus californicus* (California cone) (Conus californicus)]. Accession number D6C4M3, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:D6C4M3>

Uniprot: Kunitz-type serine protease inhibitor conotoxin Cal9.1a [*Californiconus californicus* (California cone) (Conus californicus)]. Accession number D2Y488, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:D2Y488>

Uniprot: Conotoxin Cl14.9 [*Californiconus californicus* (California cone) (Conus californicus)]. Accession number D6C4J8, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:D6C4J8>

Uniprot: Alpha-conotoxin CIB (C1.2) [*Conus catus* (Cat cone)]. Accession number P0DPT2, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:P0DPT2>

Uniprot: Conotoxin Fla16d (Conotoxin Fla16.1) [Cleaved into: Conotoxin fla16a; Conotoxin fla16b; Conotoxin fla16c] [*Conus flavidus* (Yellow Pacific cone)], Accession number V5V893, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:V5V893>

Uniprot: Sigma-conotoxin GVIIIA [*Conus geographus* (Geography cone) (Nubecula geographus)]. Accession number P58924, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:P58924>

Uniprot: Conotoxin Mr15.2 (Mr094) [*Conus marmoreus* (Marble cone)]. Accession number P0DM19, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:P0DM19>

Uniprot: Conotoxin mr3g (Mr3.6) [*Conus marmoreus* (Marble cone)]. Accession number P0C1N5, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:P0C1N5>

Uniprot: Conotoxin Pu6.1 [*Conus pulicarius* (Flea-bitten cone)]. Accession number D2DGD8, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:D2DGD8>

Uniprot: Alpha-conotoxin-like Pu1.5 [*Conus pulicarius* (Flea-bitten cone)]. Accession number P0C8U9, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:P0C8U9>

Uniprot: Putative alpha-conotoxin Qc alphaL-1, QcaL-1 [*Conus quercinus* (Oak cone)]. Accession number A1X8B8, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:A1X8B8>

Uniprot: Contryphan-R (Bromocontryphan) [Cleaved into: [Des-Gly1]-contryphan-R] [*Conus radiatus* (Rayed cone)]. Accession number P58786, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:P58786>

Uniprot: Rho-conotoxin TIA, Rho-TIA [*Conus tulipa* (Fish-hunting cone snail) (Tulip cone)]. Accession number P58811, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:P58811>

Uniprot: Conotoxin 10 [*Conus virgo* (Virgin cone)]. Accession number Q5K0C5, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:Q5K0C5>

Uniprot: Conotoxin Vi15a (Vi15.1) [*Conus virgo* (Virgin cone)]. Accession number B3FIA5, <https://identifiers.org/Uniprot:B3FIA5>

Zenodo: Underlying data for ‘Toxin-like peptides in plasma, urine and faecal samples from COVID-19 patients’, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4903154>¹⁶

This project contains the following underlying data:

- Data file 1: Toxins.fasta
- Data file 2: Toxins.mgf

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license \(CC-BY4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Consent

The human biological samples used in the experimentation were collected and used with the expressed free and informed written consent of the person from whom the material was taken, according to current legislation.

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Declarations

The scientific output expressed does not imply a policy position of the European Commission. Neither the European Commission nor any person acting on behalf of the Commission is responsible for the use that might be made of this publication.

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